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GIS platform development for managing human-wildlife conflicts in the Carpathians

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SUMMARY

A GIS platform prototype was created to store, analyse, visualize, and manage geospatial data for real-time decision-making and manage human-wildlife conflicts and coexistence in the Ukrainian Carpathian region's model territories. A specialised geodatabase in GDB format was developed in the licensed software product ESRI ArcGIS Pro 3.2.2 for spatial-temporal analysis and visualisation of the obtained data. The database was developed using PostgreSQL and PostGIS DBMS to store and supplement information. A functional prototype of GIS service was created. The developed system allows to enter and work with data on conflicts between large carnivores (grey wolf, brown bear, Eurasian lynx) and farmers/beekeepers, as well as visualize the necessary parameters for making appropriate decisions on conflict management at the landscape level by stakeholders (local authorities, forestry, nature conservation institutions, farmers and beekeepers' associations, etc.). The product allows for the effective use of existing information to improve the level of coexistence between local communities and wildlife through preventive measures in the region and to integrate the obtained data into regional land management and species conservation plans. The GIS system can be scaled for sustainable regional, national, and international levels.

Keywords: GIS platform, decision-making, human-wildlife conflicts.

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Introduction

The research of human-wildlife conflicts, particularly between humans and large carnivores (grey wolf – *Canis lupus*, brown bear – *Ursus arctos*, Eurasian lynx – *Lynx lynx*), is attractingly increasing attention from scientists and decision-makers – the share of publications on this topic has been actively growing in recent years (Qamer et al., 2023). The importance of effective landscape management, environmental safety, conservation of rare animal populations, and sustainable economic development of local communities in natural and anthropogenic areas dictates the demand for such research. Qualitative and quantitative monitoring data on the number of large carnivores and human-wildlife conflicts on different territories are the basis for developing and implementing GIS platforms for practical management solutions for these issues (Narayan & Rana, 2023).

Now, the negative consequences of conflicts decrease over time in different territories across Europe, indicating the adaptation of livestock owners and authorities to the presence of carnivores by increasing conflict prevention efforts, such as electric fences, herding dogs, communication campaigns, online GIS platforms, etc. (Singer et al., 2023). Thus, state programs and GIS services in European countries are being implemented to prevent and mitigate conflicts with large carnivores (Papp C-R et al., 2022).

Unfortunately, there is almost no research devoted to conflicts between large carnivores and humans in the territory of Ukraine and governmental programs on these issues (Cherepanyn et al., 2024). But without effective GIS products, allow to improve the level of coexistence between local communities and wildlife and to integrate the obtained data into regional land management and species conservation plans – long-term programs for managing landscapes, sustainable economic development of the communities, and conservation populations of rare species will be ineffective (Marchini et al., 2021). Achieving these in natural and anthropogenic landscapes remains challenging and requires comprehensive solutions.

Thus, the tasks of this research are to create an GIS service prototype to store, analyse, visualize, and manage geospatial monitoring data on structure, dynamics, and spatial distribution of conflicts between large carnivores (wolf, bear, and lynx) and farmers/beekeepers in model regions of the Ukrainian Carpathians for real-time decision-making and adequate manage (preventing and mitigating) human-wildlife conflicts in nature protected and anthropogenic landscapes.

Method

Collecting, pre-processing, and structuring information using Microsoft Excel software and Sensing Clues platform tools. To ensure the ability of spatial-temporal analysis and visualisation of the obtained data, a specialised geodatabase in GDB format was developed in the licensed software product ESRI ArcGIS Pro 3.2.2, which allows storing, processing, and analysing geospatial information using different cartographic visualisation techniques.

A database structure for storing and editing information about conflicts between large carnivores and farmers/beekeepers in the Ukrainian Carpathians from 2018 to 2023 was developed based on collected field data using PostgreSQL and PostGIS DBMS (Martinho et al., 2020; Kranjčić et al., 2021). An interface for entering and editing data was developed. Existing information about conflicts was entered into the database. A service based on GeoServer was deployed to visualize geospatial data (Růžička, 2016).

Styles for data visualisation on GIS platform and a system of data filters for information search were developed. Interactive map controls for user interaction with data were created. A prototype of GIS service, conflicts between large carnivores and farmers/beekeepers in the Ukrainian Carpathians from 2018 to 2023 were evaluated, corrected, and published.

This approach effectively processes collected data and integrates it into a geographic information model. It also allows for analysing and displaying these data on modern GIS platforms, providing broad access to the study results for researchers, managers, and decision-makers.

Results

The database on large carnivores and farmers/beekeepers conflicts in the Ukrainian Carpathians from 2018 to 2023 was developed using PostgreSQL/PostGIS DBMS to store and supplement information (Figure 1). A functional GIS service prototype was created and hosted on the GeoServer, containing 91 farms and 24 apiaries in the highland research areas, which were chosen for the human-wildlife conflicts.

Figure 1. PostgreSQL/PostGIS Geodatabase Scheme of Human-Wildlife Conflicts in the Ukrainian Carpathians

Information on human-wildlife conflicts in the Ukrainian Carpathians is structured in the interactive online system for administration according to the following key categories: name of the farms/apiaries; district of location; geographical coordinates; economic type (beekeeper, sheep owner, cattle owner, etc.); presence/absence of conflict during the year; a species of large carnivores that causes conflicts (wolf, bear, lynx); consequences of conflicts (number of killed/injured domestic animals or destroyed/damaged beehives); the presence of dogs to protect the farms; breed of dogs; presence/absence of an electric fence to protect the farms/apiaries; the year of electric fences installation; presence/absence of conflicts after electric fences installation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. An example of the administration interface of GIS on human-wildlife conflicts with the possibility of managing users and distinct groups, filtering by roles and other parameters.

A GIS service based on GeoServer was deployed to visualize geospatial data for interested stakeholders (local authorities, forestry enterprises, nature conservation institutions, farmers, beekeepers' associations, etc). Such an online GIS service can be shared between researchers, managers, and decision-makers for making effective decisions and expressing analysis of the human-wildlife conflicts, hotspot areas, and most critical farms (locations and areas) for species and landscape management (Figure 3).

Figure 3. An example of the visualization interface of geospatial data on conflicts between large carnivores and farms for interested parties, with the possibility of filtering by selected parameters.

Conclusions

The prototype of the GIS system effectively supports the collection, storage, analysis, and visualisation of geospatial data on human-wildlife conflicts in the Ukrainian Carpathians. By structuring detailed information on conflicts with large carnivores and integrating it into an accessible digital format, the system enables faster, data-driven decision-making and supports landscape-level conflict prevention strategies.

The tool is user-friendly, does not require deep technical expertise, and can be used by many stakeholders, including local authorities, conservation institutions, and farmer associations. Furthermore, the system can be scaled and adapted for sustainable resource and species management at regional and national levels, contributing to improved coexistence between humans and wildlife.

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References

Cherepanyn, R. M., Zelenchuk, Y. I., Yamelynets, T. S., Vykhor, B. I., & Andreychuk, Y.M. (2024). Large carnivores and farmers/beekeepers conflicts in the Ukrainian Carpathians: structure, dynamics, spatial distribution and effective coexistence measures. *Biosystems Diversity*, 32(3), 324–333. <https://doi.org/10.15421/012435>

Kranjčić, N., Đurin, B., Dogančić, D., & Plantak, L. (2021). Improving Management of Spatial Data through Spatial Database. *Environmental Sciences Proceedings*, 5(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/IECG2020-08865>

Marchini, S, Ferraz, K. M. P. M. B., Foster, V., Reginato, T., Kotz, A., Barros, Y., Zimmermann, A., & Macdonald, D. W. (2021). Planning for Human-Wildlife Coexistence: Conceptual Framework, Workshop Process, and a Model for Transdisciplinary Collaboration. *Frontiers in Conservation Science*, 2, 752953. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcosc.2021.752953>

Martinho, N., Almeida, J.-P. d., Simões, N. E., & Sá-Marques, A. (2020). UrbanWater: Integrating EPANET 2 in a PostgreSQL/PostGIS-Based Geospatial Database Management System. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(11), 613. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi9110613>

Narayan, E., & Rana, N. (2023). Human-wildlife interaction: past, present, and future. *BMC Zool.*, 8(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40850-023-00168-7>.

Qamer, R., Zishan, A. W., Nahila, A., Jahangeer, A. B., Mohd, H., & Shreekar, P. (2023). Human-wildlife conflict: A bibliometric analysis during 1991–2023. *Regional Sustainability*, 4(3), 309–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsus.2023.08.008>

Papp, C.-R., Scheele, B. C., Rákósy, L., & Hartel, T. (2022). Transdisciplinary deficit in large carnivore conservation funding in Europe. *Nature Conservation*, 49, 31–52. <https://doi.org/10.3897/natureconservation.49.81469>

Růžička, J. (2016). Comparing the speed of Web Map Service with GeoServer on ESRI Shapefile and PostGIS. *Geoinformatics FCE CTU*, 15(1), 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.14311/gi.15.1.1>

Singer, L., Wietlisbach, X., Hickisch, R., Schoell, E. M., Leuenberger, C., den Broek, A. V., Désalme, M., Driesen, K., Lyly, M., Marucco, F., Kutal, M., Pagon, N., Papp, C. R., Milioni, P., Uzdras, R., Zihmanis, I., Zimmermann, F., Marsden, K., Hackländer, K., López-Bao, J. V., Klenzendorf, S., & Wegmann, D. (2023). The spatial distribution and temporal trends of livestock damages caused by wolves in Europe. *Biological Conservation*, 282, 110039. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2023.110039>